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Exploring the Study Circle approach in fostering change in biodiversity values among adults

Part of the Collection: Findings and Recommendations from the SHARED GREEN DEAL Social Experiments

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Executive summary of recommendations

This report presents findings of four social experiments which explored the diverse values people assign to biodiversity across different European regions using the Study Circle approach, a non-formal learning method. By fostering public engagement, education, and behavioural change, this approach aimed to inspire transformative change in biodiversity values and contribute to its preservation. As such, the Study Circles on Biodiversity held in four countries (Slovenia, Ireland, Sweden and Greece) aimed to translate high-level policy frameworks into actionable, community-driven initiatives that address biodiversity loss while fostering a just and inclusive transition as envisioned by the European Green Deal.

Based on these experiments, we offer the following recommendations:

- **Leverage the Study Circle approach to enhance adults' biodiversity knowledge and awareness**
The concept of biodiversity is not always easy to grasp. Non-formal community learning can help deep-dive into the importance of biodiversity in everyday life and the cruciality of thriving ecosystems for prosperous communities. Its interactive and participatory structure fosters an open, discussion-oriented environment. Members exchange experiences and perspectives, deepening their understanding of complex ecological relationships and the necessity for sustainable action. Above all, local actors (e.g. farmers, foresters, wildlife non-governmental organisations and other experts) should be involved so that practical knowledge can be incorporated into these projects. Through the exchange with experts from the field, a deeper understanding can be developed.
- **Strengthen citizen participation for effective biodiversity preservation**
Politics should work on promoting sustainable change by strengthening citizen participation and should take greater account of the opinions of citizens in order to align measures with their actual needs and effectively promote sustainable development. Citizen participation is an essential tool for raising awareness of preserving biodiversity, as it enables the active involvement of the community in decision-making and the implementation of conservation measures. Involving the public means that diverse perspectives and experiences are integrated, which helps to develop sustainable solutions that are accepted at the local level. Citizens can share important observations, identify local challenges and work together to develop innovative approaches to protect biodiversity. This strengthens a sense of responsibility and promotes a deeper understanding of the value of nature.
- **Integrate education and community action for biodiversity preservation**
Policy-makers should adapt educational strategies by integrating sustainability-related topics into curricula at all levels to raise awareness and foster environmentally conscious behaviour. Community projects, such as Study Circles implemented at local level, that can engage schools and local initiatives in preserving biodiversity should be encouraged, as they provide hands-on learning and strengthen community bonds. Activities like getting involved in community gardens and exploring nature trails foster direct involvement of teachers, schoolchildren, their parents and even grandparents, enhance ecological awareness, and promote sustainable practices. Intergenerational collaboration further enriches knowledge exchange and long-term commitment to nature protection, making such initiatives a valuable investment in both environmental stewardship and social cohesion. These measures will support a generation equipped to tackle sustainability challenges effectively.
- **Encourage personal engagement in biodiversity initiatives to foster knowledge sharing and inspire collective preservation efforts**
When participants feel personally connected to their projects and share their knowledge with friends and family, they play a crucial role in spreading awareness about biodiversity. A strong sense of identification not only increases personal commitment but also encourages individuals to actively share their knowledge within their social circles. To enhance this effect, targeted training and information campaigns can be designed to communicate the importance of biodiversity in clear and practical ways. Emphasising personal values can also be effective – when people recognise how biodiversity directly impacts their lives through active participation, they develop a deeper appreciation for nature. This process fosters a lasting sense of responsibility and motivates sustainable action.
- **Implement capacity-building programmes to equip communities for effective participation in biodiversity policy and decision-making**
Engaging in participatory initiatives like Study Circles can inspire greater local involvement in political processes and decision-making. By fostering dialogue and collective learning, these experiences help bridge knowledge gaps in social science and contribute to nature-positive policy development. Additionally, Study Circle outcomes can inform municipal service planning, ensuring that community-driven insights shape sustainable environmental policies. This perspective was reflected in the experiments. For example, one participant emphasised the need to increase green areas and improve waste management. Strengthening citizen engagement in governance fosters more inclusive, informed, and effective decision-making for biodiversity conservation.

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1. Introduction

This report presents findings on Preserving Biodiversity as part of the Horizon 2020 project “*Social sciences and Humanities for Achieving a Responsible, Equitable and Desirable Green Deal*” (SHARED GREEN DEAL). The EU Green Deal is a programme of policies aimed at overcoming climate change and environmental degradation by transforming the EU into a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy. The goal of SHARED GREEN DEAL is to stimulate behavioural, social and cultural change across Europe, aligned with the policy priorities of the Green Deal.

SHARED GREEN DEAL provides Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) tools to support the implementation of the Green Deal programme. In the past, SSH research on green transitions has focused on changes to either individuals (‘micro’ phenomena) or systems and collectives (‘macro’ phenomena). In contrast, SHARED GREEN DEAL focuses on ‘middle range’ (‘meso’) changes to bridge these two sets of understandings and priorities (Foulds et al., 2025). Using this innovative ‘meso’ approach, the project links societal actors to foster knowledge sharing, learn from collective experiences, and feed back into ‘macro’ policies and governance.

The SHARED GREEN DEAL consortium brings together 22 leading organisations from across Europe, including universities, research institutions, network organisations and businesses. The project is structured around six priority Green Deal topics: Clean Energy, Circular Economy, Efficient Renovations, Sustainable Mobility, Sustainable Food, and Preserving Biodiversity. Within these six themes, a total of 24 social experiments have been delivered across different EU member states and affiliated countries, working with local municipalities and not-for-profit organisations¹. Alongside this Report on Preserving Biodiversity, there are five further Reports, on the other five priority Green Deal topics of the project². Other resources related to the running of and impacts from the social experiments can also be found via www.sharedgreendeal.eu.

1.1. The aim of this experiment

Humans have recognised the value of biodiversity for thousands of years, through its utilitarian aspects as food, sources of material, or labour (Berkes, 2008; Pretty et al., 2009). Values in general are understood as the conscious or unconscious preferences, principles or ‘virtues’ of society members or the whole society (Chan et al., 2012). Value systems can be individual, cultural or institutional depending on the level at which they function. Individual values are stable, overarching ideas about what is desirable for a person and they influence behaviour and decisions in everyday life (Schwartz, 1992). While values as overarching principles guide an individual’s actions and judgements, perception is the process by which sensory impressions are interpreted and linked to existing beliefs (Pacyna, 2021). On the other hand, cultural values are beliefs, principles and norms that are considered important, correct or desirable within a particular culture. These values shape the behaviour, attitudes and social practices of members of this culture, and are central components of cultures (Hradil, 2017). This social experiment focuses on cultural values related

1 Further detail about each of the SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiments can be found in the project’s Case Study Guides (Kovács et al., 2024).

2 All reports can be accessed here: www.sharedgreendeal.eu/expt-findings

to biodiversity – these serve as a crucial meso unit that stands between macro phenomena (e.g. institutions, societies) on the one side, and micro phenomena (e.g. individual values) on the other.

Thus, the aim of this social experiment was to explore the cultural values that people place upon biodiversity, in different geographical contexts. For this we used the Study Circle approach. We expected that this non-formal learning approach about biodiversity could induce a transformative change in cultural values regarding biodiversity and would help to counteract biodiversity loss.

1.2. The policy context

The key political context for this experiment is framed by four interrelated international documents on biodiversity preservation. The Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) which promotes nature and human well-being, and was developed to foster a sustainable future, was signed in Rio de Janeiro in 1992 and entered into force in 1993. It legally binds most countries to protect biodiversity, use it sustainably and share the benefits arising from the use of genetic resources fairly. While the CBD laid the foundation for biodiversity protection on a global scale, its broad goals required more localised and actionable mechanisms.

In response to these gaps, Europe introduced two pivotal initiatives: the EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 and the European Green Deal. These initiatives aim to put biodiversity in Europe on a recovery path by 2030 and to ensure that the commitments under the CBD are translated into actionable and measurable steps within the EU member states. Both initiatives place a greater emphasis on public engagement, education, and behavioural change, making biodiversity a concern not only for policymakers but for broader society. In alignment with these regional efforts, this social experiment is also rooted in the global sustainability framework of Agenda 2030. This strategy underscores biodiversity preservation as an integral component of sustainable development, bridging global commitments with regional implementation.

Beyond being a foundation for sustainable development, biodiversity also holds significant cultural values for communities as expressed, for example, in communal berry-picking with friends or family in the forest. Addressing these values is essential to foster public awareness and support for biodiversity preservation, which is a core goal of this social experiment. To encourage people to develop an awareness of certain issues, it is essential to address their value system. There are different value concepts associated with biodiversity. In addition to well-known instrumental values, there are also intrinsic values, which recognise the inherent value of biodiversity itself, as well as relational values, which are based on desirable relationships between humans and nature (Raymond, 2022).

However, current policy usually only takes into account a limited selection of such values, which means that many different meanings that biodiversity and nature has for people are largely ignored (Pascual et al. 2022). Recognising these diverse values of biodiversity, the social experiments aimed to highlight and explore them through Study Circles on Biodiversity (hereafter: Study Circles). These participatory processes facilitated deeper engagement with how nature's value is perceived and preserved by the participants.

The main objective of this social experiment is thus directly linked to the '2.1.7. Preserving and restoring ecosystems and biodiversity' objective of the European Green Deal by tackling climate and environmental-related challenges through the Study Circles across Europe. In summary, the Study Circles on Biodiversity aimed to translate these high-level policy frameworks into actionable, community-driven initiatives that address biodiversity loss while fostering a just and inclusive transition as envisioned by the European Green Deal.

2. The social experiment: the Study Circle approach

2.1. Implementing the Study Circle approach

Box 1. Cultural values of biodiversity

In this social experiment, the meso unit was defined as cultural values of biodiversity. Cultural values of biodiversity can include biodiversity-friendly practices which are integrated into cultural identity (such as beekeeping), or place-based identities that shape biodiversity protection (e.g. traditional meadows rich in wildlife). These operate as 'meso' phenomena as they are deeply embedded in local communities, traditions, and shared social norms; they bridge between individual values and perceptions of biodiversity (micro) and institutional frameworks and national and international policies (macro).

The Preserving Biodiversity stream, tackling one of the six SHARED GREEN DEAL topics, used the Study Circle approach to implement social experiments in four countries. This approach aimed to better take into account specific local circumstances, needs and challenges and to develop tailored solutions. The Study Circles were designed as practice-oriented measures to induce changes in the value systems of the participants in relation to biodiversity. In the context of a Study Circle, various methods are used to promote non-formal learning in the group (Larsson and Nordvall 2010):

- **Discussion-based learning approaches:** Participants regularly discuss the topic, with everyone having the opportunity to contribute their own experiences and perspectives. This promotes a deeper understanding and enables participants to learn from each other.
- **Participatory methods:** All members are actively involved in the learning process, which is supported by the structure of the approach. There are no hierarchical teacher-student relationships, but rather equal participation by all.
- **Experiential learning:** In addition to theoretical discussions, practical, action-oriented activities are integrated. This strengthens the understanding and application of what has been learned in real life.
- **Self-directed learning:** Participants set their own learning goals and regularly reflect on their learning progress. This autonomy promotes motivation and engagement.
- **Collaborative learning:** The group works together on solutions, shares knowledge and supports each other. This strengthens social bonds and promotes group identity.

As part of a multi-stage selection process, four local partners were chosen from a total of 85 applications received from non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and local authorities from various regions of Europe interested in delivering this SHARED GREEN DEAL social experiment. The geographical distribution of local partners across Europe was also taken into consideration in the

selection process. Therefore, Study Circles were conducted in Tolmin (Slovenia), Athens (Greece), Stockholm (Sweden) and Ballyhoura (Ireland).

Four groups of adults were formed in these four countries. Each local partner selected participants for the Study Circles by drawing on their local networks, including community organisations, social programmes, newspapers and social media.

During the implementation of the Study Circles, the local partners consistently encouraged inclusivity and respect for all viewpoints, created safe and accessible spaces for the meetings, prevented hierarchical structures and unbalanced group dynamics, and shared notes and observations with the group to reflect on progress and challenges. These groups of adults met monthly over one year with a summer break.

All four Study Circles not only imparted theoretical knowledge about biodiversity, but also made it tangible in a practical way. Through the organised biodiversity walks in the respective regions, the participants were able to directly apply and deepen what they had learned. These walks provided a valuable opportunity to experience the diversity of local flora and fauna at first hand, to better understand ecological relationships and to consolidate their theoretical knowledge in a practical context.

In addition, in each country, specific topics related to biodiversity were dealt with directly in the respective region. There were also creative sessions, such as handicraft workshops. At the end of each Study Circle, a final public event was organised, at which the learning goals and actions were made accessible and presented to the wider public and local communities. For details of the programme over the year, see Figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1. Time frame of the Study Circles conducted within the SHARED GREEN DEAL project.

The Study Circles approach provided a way to explore how adults engage with the topic of biodiversity and how their value systems evolve through group interaction. By encouraging informal reflection on shared and individual values Study Circles invited participants to explore local cultural traditions and practices. This process aimed to stimulate shifts in participants’ value systems – including their perceptions, knowledge and behaviour. We envisioned that such transformative change would also foster a deeper understanding of the social processes that connect individuals to broader societal structures.

By informing the public about the results of the Study Circles at the respective final events, and through mutual exchange of ideas with these attendees, we ensured the interventions did not only engage the Study Circle participants, but also wider communities. This reflects our commitment to exploring change beyond the individual level.

Each Study Circle was composed of between 13 and 37 adults who were motivated to learn more about biodiversity (for details see Table 2.1). Of the total 86 participants in all Study Circles, 31 had experienced social isolation (e.g. due to COVID-19)³. Additionally, since diversity is at the heart of the project, local partners sought to ensure group diversity in terms of age (ranging from 18 to 71 years), gender⁴ (33 men, 52 women, 1 non-binary), and occupation (including students, employees, retirees).

Table 2.1. Basic details of Study Circles’ participants.

Local partner organisation and country	Type of area	Gender	Participants who had experienced social isolation
Posoški razvojni centre (Slovenia)	rural	11 women 2 men	8
NGO Ballyhoura Development CLG (Ireland)	rural	13 women 8 men	5
Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm (Sweden)	urban	19 women 17 men 1 non-binary	13
Municipality of Amaroussion (Greece)	urban	9 women 6 men	5

³ Social isolation was a theme considered within this social experiment, but is not a main focus for this report.

⁴ When collecting data on participants’ genders, we asked them to self-identify. We report genders using the terms “man”, “woman” and “non-binary”, in accordance with World Health Organisation guidance on sex and gender terminology. See: <https://www.who.int/health-topics/gender>

Study Circles in
a) Slovenia,
b) Greece,
c) Sweden
and
d) Ireland

2.2. Data collection: interviews

In order to record the changes in values around biodiversity, qualitative interviews were conducted (10 interviews per Study Circle). Nine participants and one mentor were interviewed for each Study Circle (except in Sweden, where one interview included two participants, so there were 11 participants in total). A structured interview guide was used to systematically document transformations over the duration of the Study Circle. Details on the methodological approach can be found in the Methods Appendix to this report and in the project’s case study guides (Kovács et al., 2025).

Table 2.2. Interview participant characteristics.

Country	Total number of interviewees	Participant gender	Age range
Slovenia	10	Men: 1 Women: 9 Non-binary: 0	18 to 24: 0 25 to 44: 4 45 to 64: 5 65 and over: 1
Ireland	10	Men: 4 Women: 6 Non-binary: 0	18 to 24: 0 25 to 44: 5 45 to 64: 2 65 and over: 3
Sweden	11	Men: 5 Women: 5 Non-binary: 1	18 to 24: 1 25 to 44: 2 45 to 64: 5 65 and over: 3
Greece	10	Men: 3 Women: 7 Non-binary: 0	18 to 24: 0 25 to 44: 8 45 to 64: 2 65 and over: 0

When quoting from our interview transcripts, we use a reference code to protect participant identities. This includes a country code as follows: Slovenia (SI), Sweden (SE), Ireland (IE) and Greece (EL). Each interview has been allocated a number, with this acting as a unique marker for each participant in that location. We have also chosen to include the participant’s gender and whether they were a Study Circle participant or Study Circle mentor, as these are important characteristics for us in contextualising our data and claims.

3. Transformations in cultural values around biodiversity

In this section we present findings from the interviews on how our Study Circles engaged with culture, traditions and local practices (3.1) and how this led to changes at the individual level (3.2) and community level (3.3). In section 3.4 we reflect on how social and technical elements co-evolved throughout these experiments.

3.1. Engaging with culture, traditions and local practices

The Study Circles fostered engagement with biodiversity through experiential learning, collaborative discussions, and community-based activities. While participants did not explicitly discuss cultural values – perhaps because this is an abstract concept – their statements often reflected on cultural and traditional aspects of biodiversity.

Biodiversity activities within the Study Circles were often intertwined with cultural elements, such as traditional feasts, historical landmarks, and local folklore. For example, in Slovenia, the final event was linked with Gregorjevo, a Slovenian spring holiday, connected to birds. One participant said of this event:

“I think all those who were there, what they experienced, I think it will leave them with a lot. For me, for example, it brought back memories of when my children were in kindergarten, because they also had Gregorjevo; they went to look for sweets in the bushes [old tradition on this day], and it was such a nice feeling.” [SI03, woman, Study Circle participant]

In Ireland, participants explored the properties of Hazel and its traditional uses, which deepened their understanding of biodiversity in practical ways:

“I did particularly like the thing about how you can grow Hazel, and how it’s so renewable and then what you can use it for. I mean, we used it in a fairly basic way for hanging baskets - but it also showed you how useful it can be in other ways.” [IE03, man, Study Circle participant]

Participants also valued the collective, collaborative nature of the process. The Study Circles created a space where they could exchange ideas (including about these cultural and traditional aspects) and engage in stimulating conversations. Many expressed that this collaborative learning approach deepened their engagement with biodiversity and reinforced their motivation to continue learning.

While cultural values related to biodiversity were not explicitly discussed, the Study Circles fostered an implicit connection between biodiversity knowledge and local traditions. Through hands-on activities, collaboration, and expert interactions, the meso intervention enabled participants to engage more deeply with biodiversity, develop practical skills, and create meaningful community connections. This led to changes both at the individual level and community level, as detailed in the following sections.

3.2. Changes at the individual level

At the individual level the majority of participants spoke about enhanced awareness, broadening perspectives, paying more attention to details in nature, and better connection to nature – in short, mainly they reported shifts in their attitudes and perceptions. Many respondents shared that their participation in the Study Circles – such as through activities like farm visits – exposed them to topics related to biodiversity. This experience helped them gain a broader understanding of the significance of biodiversity. A key aspect highlighted was the participants' heightened sensitivity to various habitats and the organisms that inhabit them, including wildflowers and bees or other pollinators.

“...I definitely started to appreciate more the green spaces around my municipality and my city in general. I hadn't realised their value. After our meetings I started to understand the value they have both for your daily life and for our history as citizens here in the Municipality of Maroussi and the history of how food is made and where it comes from. These are all cultural elements. So I was not aware of this before I knew about it through the meetings.” [EL07, woman, Study Circle participant]

One participant mentioned that she has gained a deeper understanding, which enables her to see things from new perspectives.

“I've gained deeper insight into the understanding, I think you can never stop learning, it feels like there's always something, but yes, I've learnt more about all the themes, or what we've been talking about, so that there are more species, more yes, and also how to see. How to look at different things, like with new eyes and new knowledge.” [SE05, woman, Study Circle participant]

These quotations clearly demonstrate that the Study Circles have played a significant role in raising environmental awareness and fostering a deeper understanding of interconnectedness of nature. One participant even attributes a key role to awareness:

“...awareness is key I think, most people just live their lives and kind of forget that biodiversity is all around them...” [IE01, woman, Study Circle participant]

Another change identified at the individual level relates to learning and knowledge. Participants appear to have expanded their knowledge through the Study Circles, gaining more detailed insights into ecological interrelationships, which, in turn, has deepened their appreciation of biodiversity.

“...because I gained more knowledge about it, I definitely understood more and the importance of maybe the simple things like the wildflowers, the likes of the habitats that I wasn't exposed to before like because we learnt more about we'll say the solitary bees you know about the nocturnal biodiversity, so I think definitely my understanding has broadened so much and I think it definitely I value biodiversity way more than I did before...” [IE04, man, Study Circle mentor]

However, for some participants, the Study Circle experience primarily reaffirmed their existing knowledge of biodiversity. A few mentioned that while they did not discover new information or changes through the Study Circles, their participation in this non-formal learning environment helped to validate and strengthen their prior understanding and respect for nature.

“Because of my job, I've worked and read a lot about biodiversity. So it's not, I don't think it's changed anything in me. I've always placed a high value on biodiversity.” [EL09, woman, Study Circle participant]

We also noticed certain behavioural changes. Some Study Circle participants shared that they now spend more time outdoors, walk through nature more mindfully, and show greater respect for the environment, including giving more space to animal and plant habitats. This mindfulness extends to

their own surroundings and activities like hiking. For instance, one participant noted that she has developed “a more holistic view” [SI06, woman, Study Circle participant] when engaging with nature.

3.3. Impacts on local communities

In the interviews, the participants mainly spoke about values on an individual level. However, it was evident that the insights gained during the Study Circles also brought about some changes at the community level. The interviews indicated and the local partners reported that biodiversity initiatives – such as participating in Citizen Science activities like bird-counting – are welcomed as a way to translate global biodiversity preservation policies into community-driven initiatives that address biodiversity loss.

Through the knowledge gained in the group, participants felt motivated to educate others, particularly within their families, about biodiversity and its significance. They expressed an increased willingness to share their insights with those around them, contributing to the potential for long-term systemic change. In this respect, the family, school and kindergarten teachers play a particularly important role.

“But I use the information and give it out to hundreds of children in the job that I do [as a teacher] on a day-to-day basis, so it really acted to spread awareness in a huge way because even with the small numbers of participants, we were all feeding back to our communities and back to our workplaces, and suddenly making people aware in a gentle kind of a way about the loss of biodiversity and how it really affects us at a core here in the Ballyhoura [region].” [IE10, woman, Study Circle participant]

In Slovenia, participants took part in a bird-counting initiative as part of a Citizen Science project that combined biodiversity education with hands-on engagement. One of the participants, a kindergarten teacher, involved the children in her class in the activity. To support their observations, the teacher and children made bird cakes, which they hung around the kindergarten and at their homes. This helped attract local bird species, making it easier for the children to observe and count them. The activity not only deepened their understanding of biodiversity but also created a meaningful, intergenerational learning experience.

“We made bird cakes, we went to get suet [animal fat], we cooked it in the kindergarten, and the children took the bird cakes home, so that attracted the birds to their neighbourhood.” [SI06, woman, Study Circle participant]

One Study Circle mentor said: “What has largely changed is my sensitivity to learning what plants are around me and using it as a game and as a learning tool for my children.” [EL10, woman, Study Circle mentor]

In addition, the Study Circle approach, which involved learning about biodiversity in a group setting, allowed participants to exchange knowledge and experiences, fostering mutual learning and collaboration.

“...But I still felt that there were several sources of knowledge and not just one and that you welcomed that information. And it felt like everyone was super engaged and it was that there were interesting conversations, kind of.” [SI08, non-binary, Study Circle participant]

The opportunity to interact with invited experts played a crucial role in expanding participants’ understanding of biodiversity challenges, particularly regarding human impacts such as the fertilizer use in agriculture. Participants appreciated the accessibility of expert knowledge and the ability to apply it to their local contexts:

“In a short time, experts shared a great deal of information, so you learn a lot in a short time.” [SL08, woman, Study Circle participant]

Many participants highlighted the sharing of knowledge, particularly in defining biodiversity and understanding its significance. In this way, the learning process itself became a valued experience.

With regard to collaboration, it would also be conceivable to establish further networks in order to multiply the knowledge acquired in the Study Circle:

“...So, the idea is to set up certain didactic or thematic points where, also with certain didactic material available at each point, the interested public, in general, I will say families with children, with grandchildren, could be able to visit, and...the Adult Education Centre, which covers adult education, as well as schools and kindergartens, could spend quality time there, learning or researching or observing, or, indeed, it would be one such meeting place for people.” [SI01, woman, Study Circle mentor]

3.4. Sociotechnical evolution: interactions between technology, materials, and social outcomes

We now address sociotechnical evolution⁵, a theme of the project. The integration of technology into the Study Circles was highlighted as a key factor positively influencing their social outcomes. In the Slovenian and Swedish Study Circles, the use of the ‘Bird Buddy’, a bird feeder equipped with a camera, allowed participants to observe and document birds while they fed. This technology sparked further engagement, with some participants creating bird feeding stations in their own gardens to continue observing bird species at home. This demonstrates how the use of ‘Bird Buddy’ inspired participants to deepen their connection with bird species, fostering biodiversity-related values. The social impact of this technology is evident in the following participant’s quote.

“The bird feeder, the Bird Buddy...turned out to be successful...This idea was then adopted at [school name], and they were very happy that we then set up this bird feeder on their piece of green space. So I think it was very successful, because then other teachers also got information about this Study Circle [and] the pupils, so that with application and communication of learning about birds, the very purpose was achieved.” [SI01, woman, Study Circle mentor]

Similarly, the Irish Study Circle emphasised technical skills that served a social purpose, particularly through a photography workshop. Participants learned to take photos with smartphones and cameras during nature walks, encouraging them to focus on biodiversity while developing photography skills. This hands-on activity fostered peer learning, as participants taught one another and shared techniques. The workshop culminated in a final photo exhibition during the Study Circle’s final event. This activity was described by participants as highly successful.

“I think the variety of workshops was a huge success. So, from bird watching to the sustainability goals, we had a workshop on that to make us more knowledgeable on that. Then the photography workshop we had so it just kind of catered for everything.” [IE05, woman, Study Circle participant].

These examples illustrate how sociotechnical interactions – through the integration of technology and practical skills – enhanced participants’ engagement with biodiversity, fostered social connections, and encouraged long-term investment in conservation efforts.

⁵ In this project, the term ‘sociotechnical’ refers to an understanding of social and technical elements as co-constructive. In other words, social phenomena (such as communities, relationships and emotions) both shape and are shaped by technologies (such as buildings, infrastructures and devices). Our analysis therefore pays attention to how social dynamics shape technical ones, and vice versa.

4. Learning points and recommendations for policy and governance

Understanding the progress and challenges of Study Circles is essential for evaluating their impact and effectiveness. Over a 12-month period, our four local partners completed monthly surveys to track developments and identify obstacles. At the end of the Study Circles, each partner compiled a report summarising key insights and successes. The analysis of these reports not only highlights achievements within individual regions but also offers valuable guidance for policymakers and governance, contributing to the broader discourse on community-driven learning and efforts on preserving biodiversity. In addition, recommendations given by Study Circles' participants in interviews have been also taken into consideration here. Explicit inputs from involved local partners and participants are provided in Table 4.1 on the next page.

4.1. Successes and lessons from the Study Circles

The successes and lessons learned in the four countries – Slovenia, Ireland, Sweden and Greece – offer valuable insights that apply not only to these specific regions but could also be transferred to many other rural and urban areas. The challenges and opportunities in the field of biodiversity, such as the lack of scientific data, the lack of public transport in rural areas, or the need to seek closer connection to nature, promote local participation and knowledge sharing, are often also encountered in other rural and urban communities. The positive effects of Study Circles and similar participatory learning approaches can therefore also contribute to raising awareness of biodiversity and strengthening social cohesion in other rural and urban contexts in other European countries.

As already highlighted in previous sections, cultural values on biodiversity represent an important meso unit. In order to implement interventions in meso phenomena, attempts should be made to build shared cultural values of biodiversity so that people with different backgrounds and interests ideally develop a common interest in a particular matter on biodiversity (or other investigated topic). Non-formal learning in a group is particularly suitable for this purpose (see Section 2 for more details). Such learning is best supported when the group is facilitated and enriched by some degree of expert participation, and visits to local surroundings which stimulate sharing of practical experiences.

Table 4.1. Successes and lessons learned through Study Circles in four countries.

Local partner organisation and country	Successes	Lessons learned
Soča Valley Development Centre (Slovenia)	Participants gained in-depth knowledge about biodiversity, especially birds and pollinators. The plan to convert a community garden into an outdoor classroom, featuring insect hotels and bird feeders, was well-received. The Study Circle fostered democratic participation and collaboration, with a mix of theoretical and hands-on learning proving effective.	Participants met personal learning objectives, which were adapted to their interests. The garden transformation serves as a community outcome, and future expansion of the Study Circle is encouraged. It is recommended that policymakers support networking between institutions like adult education centres and schools.
NGO Ballyhoura Development CLG (Ireland)	In the Ballyhoura catchment area, there was strong enthusiasm for biodiversity, though often lacking scientific grounding. Participants wanted to learn more about their local ecosystems and valued their connection to nature. Informal discussions during breaks fostered biodiversity exchanges, highlighting the importance of learning outside formal settings.	Isolated community members need support and encouragement to build confidence and participate in activities. Limited public transport hampers access to biodiversity events. Participants often feel their local knowledge is undervalued politically. Local Study Circles have promoted active engagement.
Environment and Health Department of the Municipality of Stockholm (Sweden)	Approximately 30 participants of diverse backgrounds took part in ten Study Circle sessions, giving highly positive feedback and indicating successful implementation. Collaboration with local organisations and two successful public events highlighted the initiative's achievements.	Engaging citizens is essential, especially regarding local biodiversity. While many participants enrich discussions, it can be challenging to ensure everyone's voice is heard. Collaboration with the local 'Nature School' was beneficial, emphasising the need for networking among institutions. A clearly structured programme is important, along with participant involvement in design and inclusion of diverse experts. These insights underline the importance of citizen participation, community building, and structured programming in biodiversity projects.
Municipality of Amaroussion (Greece)	Participants from diverse backgrounds brought varied interests to the learning trail, fostering greater awareness of biodiversity conservation. Many sought closer contact with nature and engaged in plant care or garden creation. Participants became ambassadors for local conservation, sharing knowledge with their networks and developed a stronger social bond with each other. An initiative arose to label plants in the 'Synggros Urban Forest', enhancing appreciation for the area.	Mutual exchange and support among team members are vital for gaining knowledge. Site visits highlighted the need to protect endemic species and promote awareness of their importance in local ecosystems, as well as the potential threats posed by non-endemic plants. The results of such Study Circle and citizen engagement activities can inform and shape municipal services planning in regard to nature protection.

4.2. Recommendations for policy and governance on biodiversity preservation

By reflecting on the above lessons learned and successes in Study Circles, we suggest various recommendations for use of the Study Circle approach within the wider EU context to support community-driven learning and engagement in preserving biodiversity. Particularly in the interviews, it became clear that the Study Circles inspired the participants to make recommendations or ideas regarding governance.

- **Leverage the Study Circle approach to enhance adults' biodiversity knowledge and awareness**

The concept of biodiversity is not always easy to grasp. Non-formal community learning can help deep-dive into the importance of biodiversity in everyday life and the vital importance of thriving ecosystems for prosperous communities. Its interactive and participatory structure fosters an open, discussion-oriented environment. Members exchange experiences and perspectives, deepening their understanding of complex ecological relationships and the necessity for sustainable action. Above all, local actors (e.g. farmers, foresters, wildlife non-governmental organisations and other experts) should be involved so that practical knowledge can be incorporated into these projects. Through the exchange with experts from the field, a deeper understanding can be developed.

- **Strengthen citizen participation for effective biodiversity preservation**

Politics should work on promoting sustainable change by strengthening citizen participation and should take greater account of the opinions of citizens in order to align measures with their actual needs and effectively promote sustainable development. Citizen participation is an essential tool for raising awareness of preserving biodiversity, as it enables the active involvement of the community in decision-making and the implementation of conservation measures. Involving the public means that diverse perspectives and experiences are integrated, which helps to develop sustainable solutions that are accepted at the local level. Citizens can share important observations, identify local challenges and work together to develop innovative approaches to protect biodiversity. This strengthens a sense of responsibility and promotes a deeper understanding of the value of nature.

- **Integrate education and community action for biodiversity preservation**

Policy-makers should adapt educational strategies by integrating sustainability-related topics into curricula at all levels to raise awareness and foster environmentally conscious behaviour. Community projects, such as Study Circles, that can engage schools and local initiatives in preserving biodiversity should be encouraged, as they provide hands-on learning and strengthen community bonds. Activities like community gardens and nature trails foster direct involvement of teachers, schoolchildren, their parents and even grandparents, enhance ecological awareness, and promote sustainable practices. Intergenerational collaboration further enriches knowledge exchange and long-term commitment to nature protection, making such initiatives a valuable investment in both environmental stewardship and social cohesion. Outdoor classrooms can enhance experiential learning and deepen children's and students' connection to nature. These measures will support a generation equipped to tackle sustainability challenges effectively.

- **Encourage personal engagement in biodiversity initiatives to foster knowledge sharing and inspire collective preservation efforts**

When participants feel personally connected to their projects and share their knowledge with friends and family, they play a crucial role in spreading awareness about biodiversity. A strong

sense of identification not only increases personal commitment but also encourages individuals to actively share their knowledge within their social circles. To enhance this effect, targeted training and information campaigns can be designed to communicate the importance of biodiversity in clear and practical ways. Emphasising personal values can also be effective – when people recognise how biodiversity directly impacts their lives through active participation, they develop a deeper appreciation for nature. This process fosters a lasting sense of responsibility and motivates sustainable action.

- **Implement capacity-building programmes to equip communities for effective participation in biodiversity policy and decision-making**

Engaging in participatory initiatives like Study Circles can inspire greater local involvement in political processes and decision-making. By fostering dialogue and collective learning, these experiences help bridge knowledge gaps in social science and contribute to nature-positive policy development. Additionally, Study Circle outcomes can inform municipal service planning, ensuring that community-driven insights shape sustainable environmental policies. This perspective was reflected in the experiments. For example, one participant emphasised the need to increase green areas and improve waste management. Strengthening citizen engagement in governance fosters more inclusive, informed, and effective decision-making for biodiversity conservation.

From these recommendations, we can also draw out specific insights for three levels of governance: local organisations, national policy makers and international policy (although they overlap and it is difficult to divide them strictly by level).

Local policy level: Local organisations can build a network so that different interest groups have the opportunity to work on a topic (e.g. biodiversity and nature preservation). In this way, people from different institutions (e.g. schools and adult education centres) can exchange ideas in a practical way and develop workshops in which different target groups can work together. A network could be developed in a special setting, e.g. a community garden. Another recommendation at local level is to use the form of the Study Circle to bring interested adults closer to environmental topics through non-formal learning (for example the care of hay meadows, the protection of certain species, the interaction between humans and nature in the local environment). Initiatives such as Study Circles that encourage non-formal learning should be financially supported at the local level.

National policy level: As noted above, citizen participation is an essential tool for raising awareness of preserving biodiversity. In the wider implementation of projects such as Study Circles the expertise and recommendations of citizens should be taken into account, which means that a so-called 'bottom-up' approach should be used. National policymakers should actively engage with citizens, take their perspectives and concerns into account and involve them in the decision-making process. As one participant said: *"The idea or initiatives should come from the bottom up."* [SI07, woman, Study Circle participant]; another noted: *"...policymakers need to connect with the people on the ground that are actually implementing."* [IE02, woman, Study Circle participant]

International policy level: The focus should be on international awareness-raising work on nature conservation-related topics such as biodiversity protection. Furthermore, it was mentioned in the interviews that fairer/higher compensation payments for organic farming in rural regions could support the conservation of biodiversity. If farmers have sufficient financial resources, they can invest more money in sustainable land management, which in turn helps to preserve biodiversity. The recommendations above also include an adaptation of educational strategies to sensitise young people to nature conservation and preservation of biodiversity. Aligning these educational strategies with international frameworks and best practices on biodiversity preservation can ensure consistent and effective educational programmes to engage future generations with sustainability.

5. Conclusions

The SHARED GREEN DEAL Study Circles, conducted in Slovenia, Ireland, Sweden and Greece over a 12-month period from May 2023 to April 2024, illustrate how non-formal, collaborative learning can effectively promote values, knowledge and awareness of biodiversity. The structure of these learning groups, based on volunteerism, self-organisation and democratic principles, provides a creative platform for participants to actively engage with their individual interests and values on biodiversity. The fact that Study Circle participants themselves determine the specific topics on biodiversity and discuss them enables an in-depth exchange that not only imparts knowledge, but can also further develop individual perceptions, behaviours and values on biodiversity. All these have a profound influence on participants' connection to nature. In such a learning context, participants can begin to reflect on their values with regard to the environment, leading to a lasting change in the way they think and act. Sharing experiences in a group and exploring biodiversity together not only promotes environmental awareness but also strengthens a collective sense of responsibility for protecting nature. In this way, both individual and cultural values on biodiversity can be transformed in the course of the learning process and lead to a more sustainable and environmentally conscious attitude.

The qualitative interviews conducted at the end of the Study Circles clearly demonstrated that a common goal – enhancing understanding of biodiversity through the learning process to induce a shift in values that supports biodiversity preservation – plays an important role in personal and community development. The successful balance between theoretical inputs and practical experiences, such as field trips and guided walks, creates a hands-on learning environment that not only imparts knowledge on biodiversity, but also enables participants to integrate it into their everyday lives. Biodiversity preservation thus becomes not just an abstract concept as initially perceived by some interviewees in the early stages of Study Circles, but a tangible reality that participants can integrate into their daily lives. In addition, the sense of community and joy of learning from each other about biodiversity that has developed in the Study Circles shows how important networking and social interaction are in promoting environmentally conscious behaviour.

The experiences gained during the Study Circles and the voices of the participants lead to a number of recommendations that not only serve to shape future Study Circles but are also politically relevant. The preservation of biodiversity is a complex issue and the interviews clearly showed that people's perceptions, knowledge and sometimes behaviour in relation to nature and biodiversity have fundamentally changed. All participants agree that they must take responsibility for nature in order to preserve biodiversity for future generations. This process of changing perspectives and gaining new knowledge requires certain framework conditions such as the creation and facilitation of local networks, support from the local government, and committed experts who share their knowledge and experience.

The biodiversity activities in the Study Circles were often linked to cultural elements, such as traditional feasts, historical landmarks, local folklore etc. In this way Study Circle participants sought to connect biodiversity with their traditions and make the final public events more meaningful and also intergenerational. It emerged from the interviews that community-based biodiversity initiatives such as community gardens, habitat restoration, photo exhibitions, bird counts, and field trips that combine education with recreation would be welcome and could impact other

community members by raising awareness, promoting behavioural changes, strengthening social bonds, and integrating local knowledge and tradition.

At the political level, there is an urgent need to actively promote such bottom-up projects and create local networks. Coordinating and linking different local initiatives can significantly increase the reach and impact of efforts to protect biodiversity. By supporting such actions, the government and local policymakers can not only increase interest in biodiversity preservation, but also create a fertile environment for broadening perspectives, promoting learning, encouraging behaviour change and taking concrete action at personal and community levels necessary to protect the environment for future generations.

However, the following areas would benefit from further exploration in future studies: 1) to clarify how shifts in perception of biodiversity influence behaviour, identifying when they lead to change and which specific values are most impacted by non-formal adult education, such as the Study Circle approach, 2) to find out to what extent Study Circles as a form of non-formal practical learning increase people's motivation to engage with nature protection, 3) to elaborate ways for kindergarten and school teachers to transfer and upscale knowledge about biodiversity to children and students, 4) to explore ways to reach out to people who are not yet aware of the importance of biodiversity and need to include it in their value system, and 5) to identify ways to financially support community projects and local initiatives such as community gardens. Although local initiatives thrive on volunteers, setting up and developing a local initiative always involves administrative and time efforts that should be rewarded in order to motivate people to build a local network.

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Appendix – Methods

A total of 40 structured interviews were conducted as part of the study, with 10 interviews taking place per local partner – Slovenia, Ireland, Sweden and Greece. The structured interview guide was used to systematically document these transformations over the duration of the Study Circle. These 10 interviews per Study Circle normally consisted of nine participants from the respective Study Circle and one mentor who accompanied the respective Study Circle for the entire duration. In Sweden, one interview included two participants so there were 11 interviewees in total here. When selecting the interview participants, care was taken to ensure the group's diversity in terms of age (from 18 to 71 years), gender (13 men, 27 women, 1 non-binary), and occupation (students, employees, retirees). In addition, each interviewee had to have attended at least seven study group sessions. Particular attention was paid to ensuring that at least five interview participants per local partner were affected by social isolation, for example as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The interview guides were prepared by the research team and the local partners conducted the interviews. They had received extensive training from the research team beforehand to ensure that they could conduct the interviews professionally and effectively. The interviews were transcribed verbatim and then translated into English, before being systematically coded. Interview transcripts are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15076035>.

The codebook⁶ was grounded in the pre-defined research questions and the structure of the interview guide. Categories and corresponding codes were developed accordingly, with each transcript coded independently by two researchers to ensure intercoding agreement. Following the initial coding phase, some codes were refined through an iterative process that helped reveal relevant patterns and phenomena. Values on biodiversity were operationalised by identifying specific actions, decisions, and emotional responses related to biodiversity and were categorised in 3 main categories: instrumental values, intrinsic values and relational values. Special attention was given to statements indicating behavioural changes or expanded knowledge, as potential signs of shifting value systems.

In addition to the interview data, a quantitative questionnaire was also collected, which the participants completed at the beginning and end of the Study Circle. This questionnaire provided information on how individual values related to biodiversity changed or developed over the course of the Study Circle.

Finally, each of the four local partners completed a monthly survey over a period of 12 months (duration of the Study Circles) to document the progress and challenges of the respective Study Circle. In addition, at the end of the Study Circle each local partner produced a report outlining the key learning points and successes. The analysis of these documents not only illustrates successes for the individual partner regions, but can also be helpful for policymakers and other governance actors, and so was used when writing section 4 of this report.

⁶ For access to this codebook, please contact the corresponding author.

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